

Working Paper

The limitations of the Scientific method in studying objective reality

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Abstract

Probability as a subject is poorly understood by researchers in religion and the humanities. I show some of the common corruptions of the scientific method and how the scientific method is incorrectly applied to define history and the reality of the past.

By pointing out the dangers and problems of an objectivist approach, I propose that an objective or scientific approach is ill suited to study subjects like history and religion.

Keywords: Probability, Limits, Reality, Science, Scientific method

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1. Introduction

One of the most common issues in Religion and Metaphysics is the discussion about reality and non-reality. I use the example of a bell curve to illustrate why scientific investigations of reality, especially of rare events, is prone to extreme error.

There is a larger problem that Science cannot study any qualia or subjective reality, but in this discussion I will not go there. I have covered that topic briefly in my earlier paper.¹ I will confine to studying the limits of Science in studying objective reality, a space where most scientists think that science has no limits.

2. Methods

Here is how events are described on a standard bell curve. Social Science and Humanities professors are fond of using the Bell Curve. Hence, we will studying what outcomes are and how reality is estimated with Bell Curves.

For this discussion, outcome is the mean. Outcomes B and D are close to the mean, A and E are much further from the mean and outcomes P and Q are outliers - extremely far away from the mean.

We call something reality if it falls within the normally established realms of observations and outcomes. B, C and D come under reality. A and E are on the borderline, and P and Q maybe called unreal events. However, we have to understand that P or Q can also occur as outcomes because they exist on a bell curve. At that point, an observer may well call these events unreal.

3. Discussion

Estimate of Probability:

Outcome C (the mean) is more likely to occur than outcome B or outcome D. The repetition of past events is considered a measure of truth. The area under the curve is the estimate of probability. However, that is a fancy way of saying that humans are comfortable with what has occurred in the past and are comfortable with what is most likely to happen. The problem arises when likelihood is not a measure of the truth. That happens with outcomes that are unique and rarely occur again.

A problem is created when we encounter events that have occurred only once in the history of the universe. Examples include the event of the Big Bang, origin of matter, origin of life and the origin of languages. All these are outcomes of actions in the past. How do we understand the nature and purpose of an event which has occurred once or a minimal number of times? We certainly do not have logic, present practice, or observations to guide us.

C is more likely to have occurred than B or D. However this applies for estimates likelihoods going forward. Probability works well when applied to the future. It gives us a general sense of what is more likely. However, we must remember that any outcome can happen, even outcomes that are extremely unlikely and close to impossible. We should never be surprised when that outlier event happens. Rare events are unlikely to happen, but we should never be surprised when they happen.

Outcome C is more likely to happen does not prevent P or Q from happening. The problem is evident when evaluating outcomes from the past. Was it an outlier event? If yes, how far an outlier is it. We will never know.

Example:

When we shuffle a pack of cards and lay it out on a table, what is the probability that specific combination would have occurred? The answer is:

$$\text{Probability} = \frac{1}{52!} \approx \frac{1}{8.07 \times 10^{67}}$$

However, such a low probability does not mean that the outcome did not happen. Super unlikely events happen at the time, freely, easily, and regularly. Any number of people can shuffle cards their entire life and every few seconds that most unlikely probability unfolds itself with each card player. Paradoxically, low probability events of laying out cards can be likely, frequent, and easily repeatable.

Scientific testing:

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The most common confidence levels in scientific testing are 95%, 99% and 99.9%. If one assumes any higher confidence level, the hypothesis is likely to be rejected in favour of the null hypothesis. The problem is that scientists do not dare to go beyond these confines. Radical hypothesis at the edge of physics will never be investigated because it is extraordinarily unlikely, and happened once in all of time. Science cannot be applied to rare or random events. It can only be used for predictable events.

The highest confidence level of 99.9999999% or 7-sigma is used in high-energy particle physics experiments. However, can a event that has happened once even be determined scientifically. I asked ChatGPT this question for an event that has happened only twice in all of history, This is the answer:

An event that occurs twice in the universe's entire history is about 165,000 standard deviations away from the expected rate of 1.449×10^{-10} events per year. For an event that happens only twice from the birth of the universe to its end, the sigma level is approximately 165,000.

Outcomes:

Let us apply these findings to common scientific and religious problems:

- 1) The Big Bang: This event happened only once. We can never know how or why it happened. Science is no better than religion in answering this question. Unless Science can create another universe, they are stuck with mere models and equations of possibilities. To explain these mathematical models as objective reality, and using science to explain an unlikely one-time event is a false application of science. God creating the universe, the Atman creating the universe, the universe being a simulation are all possibilities that can never be ruled out as they are one-time events. Pretending that the Big Bang is an established reality with no room for doubt is a complete misunderstanding of how statistics works.
- 2) Origin of matter: Origin of matter is a one-time event. Once can come up with infinite hypothesis about the origin of the universe and of matter. For a one-time event, how can science establish the truth or lack of truth of any of these hypotheses?
- 3) Origin of life: All life traces back to a common ancestor. How can we use science to explain a one-time event. Even if we do find a chemical way to create life sometime in the future, which is so guarantee that the past was the same as the future. Can we ever know the answer to our existence? Those scientists who pretend that science can provide all the answers to the past have no understanding off how statistics works.
- 4) Origin of languages: If Sanskrit is the mother language of all Indo-European languages, can we know how it emerged? This was a one-time event. Hindus say that the dance of Shiva as Nataraja created Sanskrit. This claim is completely untestable by Science and Science has nothing to say about this topic. This is no reason to scientifically disbelieve the Hindu version.

Objections:

Question: If some questions can never be answered, are we doomed to never know the answers?

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Answer: Just because Science has no way to objectively explain one-time historical events does not mean that there is no other tool. Advaita is a subjective way to understand the universe. It assumes that the objective universe rolls into the subjective universe, and both can be explained subjectively. Just because the West has not the foggiest idea of Advaita does not mean that other tools to explain these fundamental problems do not exist.

Question: How can Advaita or a subjective approach hope to find an answer when Science cannot?

Answer: Advaita proposes that with all events, there is only one observer, and that observer is the self. The Big Bang, origin of life etc are one-time occurrences but it did not happen in the past of the observer (as per Science), but happened when the past was present to the observer(as per Advaita). Time plays no role, because the observer is considered the same. Because the outcome happened in a real time manner before the observer, the outcome is treated as a subjective creation of consciousness, as per Advaita. Hence, Advaita is able to reduce the unknowable problems of the past to a knowable problem that can be studied, in a way that Science can never do.

Question: Advaita is one among innumerable hypotheses? Why should it be considered superior to all possible hypotheses about how the world works?

Answer: Advaita uses subjective reality to fold every possible hypothesis about the external universe into subjective reality. It then folds all subjective reality under the Atman consciousness paradigm. There is no way to contradict Advaita except by evoking another objective or subjective paradigm. However, Advaita has already folded all these paradigms under the Atman. Hence, it can be said that Advaita is the mother of all philosophies, paradigms and constructs. It begins with the simplest proposition about the universe – I exist. Even a child knows this instinctively. Advaita assumes nothing else about the universe. Every other hypothesis makes innumerable other suppositions about the world. This is why all constructs are far inferior to Advaita.

4. Conclusion

Science and scientific temper have crept into every field of human endeavour. It pretends to be capable of solving every problem that is out there. However, statistical limitations mean that science is absolutely incapable of analysing rare, unique, and one-time outcomes. For these outcomes, any number of hypotheses are possible, none of which can be evaluated by science. We have to turn to a subjectivist Advaita framework to analyse the problems that Science cannot investigate.

Science falsely claims that it can provide the evidence of what is real and what is unreal. What is likely to be more real (probabilistic) is not the same as what is absolutely real (deterministic). Science reveals a world of probability where some outcomes are more likely than others. Likelihood is different from determinism. The insistence on reality and unreality is a deterministic approach. However, statistics does not deal with determinism, it deals with

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probability. Statistics makes likelihood claims and not truth claims. Fools ignorant of statistics interpret the likelihood claims as truth claims.

Looking forward, we understand the situation perfectly for both likely and unlikely events. Statistics reveals likelihood looking forward. We cannot say what will happen but can say what is more likely to happen. In the same way, we cannot say what will not happen, but only what is most likely to happen. What is not expected to happen happens all the time. Hence, likelihood is different from deterministic reality.

In the same way, by looking at the past we can say what is likely to have happened (especially for repeatable events). However, likelihood is not the same as saying that something absolutely happened. The past is full of deterministic claims about what happened that statistics should discourage. However, for repeatable events, Science cannot surely say what did not happen because we see the results in front of us. For rare events of the past, Science is in a bind. It can neither say what happened nor what did not happen. For example, regarding the hypothesis that the world is a simulation, Science can neither claim to have a perspective on whether it is indeed a simulation or not. Science cannot handle one-time events,

References

ⁱ Aravindakshan, V. (2025). Do we live in one single objective universe? The subjectivist challenge of Advaita Vedanta. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16472907>